

COST OPTIMAL SANDWICH CONSTRUCTION BY CONTINUOUS PRODUCTION

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SUMMARY: Sandwich construction, mainly known for its weight saving potential can also offer substantial economic advantages. The cost saving potential of sandwich construction is mainly determined by the production cost of cores and panels. The advancement and automation of production processes enables today more cost efficient honeycomb materials. Folded honeycombs and their continuous production processes, developed at the K.U.Leuven, enable an automated in-line production of paper (TorHex) and thermoplastic film (ThermHex) based honeycombs. The continuous in-line application of fibre reinforced skins and direct further processing to sandwich parts qualify for mass production of honeycomb sandwich components for cost sensitive applications.

Sandwich selection charts, a graphical presentation of the effects of sandwich construction, allow a transparent comparison and cost optimisation of sandwich material combinations including production costs.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich construction, honeycomb core materials, continuous production, cost optimisation, materials selection.

INTRODUCTION

Cost optimal structural performance requires the use of material combinations, because a composition can be more efficient if each component is optimised for a certain function. Sandwich construction combines the in-plane properties of a skin material with the out-of-plane properties of a core material.

For the bending properties of a panel the stiffness and strength of a material can be used much more efficiently if the stresses act at large distances from the neutral axis. With a uniform material a thickness increase leads to an increase of both weight and material cost. Sandwich constructions use the fact that material in the core (close to the neutral axis) does not carry much in-plane stresses and does not represent the visible surface of the panel. The core can thus be made from a different, more lightweight and/or less expensive material. However, sufficient mechanical properties of the sandwich core material are necessary to prevent relative displacements of the skins with respect to each other in out-of-plane and in-plane directions.

Honeycomb core materials can offer the required out-of-plane shear and out-of-plane compression properties at an extremely low density. They are used in aerospace as preferred sandwich core material since many decades [1].

ECONOMIC ADVANTAGE OF SANDWICH MATERIALS

The advantages of the sandwich concept in bending stiffness, panel weight and panel material cost is shown in Table 1. For this comparison, the core density is assumed to be 20 times lower than the density of the skin material.

Table 1: Sandwich effect on bending stiffness, weight and material cost

Effect of sandwich construction and the sandwich thickness ratio					
• Geometrical definitions (symmetrical sandwich) Only two geometrical variables: t : skin thickness h : sandwich thickness core thickness: h-2t distance skins-neutral axis: (h-t)/2 The thickness ratio t/h is the ratio between skin thickness and total sandwich thickness. Equivalent t/h lead to equal modulus (bending and tensile).	Sandwich effect on bending stiffness weight and cost	monolithic $h_1 = 2 t_1$	thick skins $h = 2 h_1$ $t = 0.5 t_1$	thin panel $h = 1.2 h_1$ $t = 0.3 t_1$	optimised $h = 2.4 h_1$ $t = 0.06 t_1$
Relative thickness		1	2	1.2	2.4
thickness ratio t/h		0.5	0.125	0.125	0.0125
Relative bending stiffness D		1	4.625	1	1
Relative homogenized bending modulus $E = 12 D / h^2$		1	equal bending modulus 0.58		0.07
Relative weight (core density 20 times lower)		1	0.58	0.35	0.18
Relative cost with expensive core (equal cost per volume)		1	equal material cost		2.4
Relative cost with low cost core (20 times lower cost per vol.)		1	0.58	0.35	0.18

The two lowest rows of Table 1 present a material cost comparison with an expensive core and a low cost core. The material cost per weight of the low cost core is assumed to be equal to the cost per weight of the skin material. The cost for the expensive core material are assumed to be 20 times higher, leading to equal cost per volume for core and skin material. The comparison to the monolithic panel shows the large effect of the core material cost. The potential economic advantage of low cost core materials is as big as the potential weight saving due to low density core materials. It is often not realized and seldom stressed that sandwich construction can offer as much direct material cost saving as it can offer weight saving. However, the possible weight and cost advantages of sandwich construction can only be utilized if the core has sufficient mechanical properties. Furthermore, is it essential that the production adds only very little weight (glue for the core-skin bonding) and cost.

To make the complex effects of sandwich construction more transparent already during the materials selection process a graphical presentation of homogenized properties is proposed. The homogenized properties are presented in function of the sandwich thickness ratio (t/h) in sandwich selection charts. Sandwich material combinations with an equal thickness ratio have an own set of material properties (bending modulus, density and material cost). The calculation of those homogenized properties facilitates the comparison to monolithic materials.

In cost sensitive applications, sandwich material combinations are today often not treated with the required awareness of the different behaviour (shear deformations, out-of-plane compression) and the different failure modes (wrinkling, debonding). A more common use of sandwich material combinations demands additional tools to communicate the specific phenomena of sandwich construction.

SANDWICH SELECTION CHARTS

Materials selection charts (Ashby diagrams) [2] can be used to compare how efficiently different materials fulfil a certain structural function. The material efficiency per weight for bending stiffness $E^{1/3}/\rho$ (with E the elastic modulus and ρ the material density) is especially important because the bending stiffness is often the main mechanical requirement if sandwich construction is considered. For a maximal economical advantage the optimisation of the performance per weight should be part of a performance per cost optimisation.

For sandwich material selection the performance per cost of different sandwich panels needs to be compared to each other and to monolithic panels. It has been proposed earlier to display the properties of sandwich material combinations as function of the thickness ratio (t/h) in materials selection charts to facilitate the selection of sandwich materials [3]. The properties of all possible sandwich panels with this material combination (thickness ratios from 0 to 0.5) can be found on this curve. Larger material efficiency per cost in bending is at high $E^{1/3}/C_v$ ($C_v = C_w \rho$ with the material cost per weight C_w) values in the upper left corner of the diagram. As an example the material efficiency per cost in bending of the sandwich material combination of natural fibre mat reinforced polymer (NFRP) skins on a paper honeycomb core is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Sandwich materials selection chart for optimal cost (homogenized bending modulus versus cost displayed in a materials selection chart with monolithic material options)

Often a larger skin thickness needs to be selected because of strength requirements, dimpling or wrinkling failure modes, surface quality requirements or production constraints. In most cases a rather slow decrease of the material efficiency close to the optimum allows a slight increase of the thickness ratio t/h without a large penalty. Sandwich selection diagrams allow to assess the effects of non-optimal thickness ratios. Shear deformations of the core can be included into this optimisation of sandwich constructions via a shear reduced flexural modulus. In Fig. 1, shear reduction of the homogenized bending modulus is shown for a span length to panel thickness ratio of $l/h = 40$. The core shear affects the sandwich material

performance especially at larger sandwich thickness ratios. The inclusion of shear deformation leads to a dependency on the span length as well as on the loading and support conditions.

For industry, the material efficiency is especially useful because the ratios between the material efficiency of a material option and the efficiency of a reference material are saving factors. Those saving factors enable to determine directly the potential cost savings of different material options. The resulting cost saving factor (Φ_{cost}) is the factor of cost saved due to the use of sandwich construction with a less dense and/or less expensive core material. This approach to define a ratio between the material efficiency coefficient of the structured material and the material efficiency coefficient of the same unstructured material was described by Ashby in [4] and has been applied to sandwich material combinations [3].

Maximization of performance per cost for structural parts requires to find the best compromise between (structural) performance and material cost, production cost and weight. The major cost aspects interact and contradict often. This results in complex interactions during the optimisation of a design towards a maximal cost efficiency and obstructs the exploitation of the economical advantage of lightweight constructions.

A general procedure for multi-objective optimisation based on value functions was proposed by Ashby [5]. This general concept allows to include the value of every requirement into the selection and optimisation process.

The operating cost (e.g. energy consumption in transport applications) and the ecological cost (e.g. cost of recycling) are both affected by the weight, and of increasing importance since many years. To include those aspects into the comparison of materials, the benefit of weight savings has to be determined. This value of weight saving (C_{wv}) may be established by a detailed life cycle analysis or may just be assessed by asking customers how much they would pay for a weight reduction. In automotive applications for example the reduction of fuel consumption justifies that a weight saving is valued with 2 € per kg [3]. Even if the weight saving is not valued ($C_{\text{wv}} = 0$), nevertheless a sandwich material combination can lead to cost saving just by the lower amount of raw material used. Fig. 1 shows a cost advantage by a factor 1.893 compared to monolithic NFRP panels. Without considering production costs the minimal cost is reached at a thickness ratio close to $t/h = 0.04$. Due to the inclusion of the production cost per square meter (of $C_{\text{ap}} = 1 \text{ €/m}^2$) the optimum shifts to a larger thickness ratio and becomes dependent on the panel height.

The low amount of raw material required for the production of honeycomb cores can result in a more cost efficient material combination if a suitable raw material and an efficient production method are combined. Cost sensitive applications require a low cost value chain with an in-line production of honeycomb core and sandwich panel.

LOW COST SANDWICH CORE AND PANEL PRODUCTION

Honeycomb cores provide with their vertical cell walls a bi-directional support for the skins, leading to excellent specific mechanical properties. During the last two decades industry and research institutions have increased the efforts to reduce the production cost of honeycomb sandwich panels. The demands for low cost and high production capacities in many industries require automated and continuous sandwich core and panel production processes. Most aerospace honeycomb cores are adhesive bonded expanded cores produced in a batch process [1]. Low cost paper honeycombs are also produced by this traditional expansion process. Paper honeycombs with small cell size for automotive and furniture applications are furthermore commonly produced via a block of stacked corrugated cardboard sheets. Those cores are combined with glass fibre or natural fibre reinforced skins and for example used for sunroof panels and spare wheel covers. An overview of the recent advances in production processes, which may enable a widespread introduction of honeycomb sandwich constructions into non-aerospace markets, is presented in [6].

New folded honeycomb production technologies developed and patented by the K.U.Leuven enable a continuous honeycomb core and panel production by successive in-line operations. Those economic core technologies (TorHex and ThermHex) will be marketed by the spin-off company EconCore.

The TorHex paper honeycomb process uses the corrugated cardboard production technology to a maximum extent. The principal production concept is shown in Fig. 2. After the production of a single flute corrugated cardboard, the process requires only a lengthwise slitting step and a folding/turning step. Paper honeycomb cores can hereby be produced at low cost from an endless web of corrugated cardboard.

Fig. 2: TorHex folded paper honeycomb material and process; one corrugated cardboard sheet slit and turned

The thermoplastic folded honeycomb, ThermHex, has hexagonal cells and closed skin strips, which allow a fast and reliable bonding of skins onto the core (Fig. 3). ThermHex cores can be produced continuously in one production line from one endless thermoplastic film by successive in-line operations at high production speeds, with in-line lamination of skins. The internal bonding of the core by thermal fusion can be enhanced by a lower melting coating on the thermoplastic film.

Fig. 3: ThermHex thermoplastic folded honeycomb material and process; one film vacuum thermoformed, folded and welded together

CONCLUSION

Many industries request a performance to cost advantage and demand that new material solutions meet the mechanical requirements while permitting a cost reduction. The automated in-line production of honeycombs with a continuous in-line panel material production enables to reduce the production costs substantially. The raw material weight savings result thus directly in cost savings and allow the exploitation of the economical advantages of sandwich constructions. For the development of low cost sandwich applications it is furthermore essential to enable the designer of automotive parts to understand the advantages of sandwich constructions. The presented sandwich selection charts allow to determine the potential cost savings of different sandwich material combinations.

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REFERENCES

1. Bitzer, T., Honeycomb Technology, London, Chapman & Hall, 1997
2. Ashby, M.F., Materials and process selection in mechanical design, Butterworth Heinemann, Oxford, 1999
3. Pflug, J., Vangrimde, B., Verpoest, I., Material efficiency and cost effective-ness of sandwich materials, Sampe Conference, Longbeach, USA, 2003
4. Ashby, M.F., Materials and Shape, Acta Metall. Mater., vol.39/6, pp.1025, 1991
5. Ashby, M.F., Multi-Objective Optimization in Material Design and Selection, Acta Metall. Mater., vol. 48/1, pp. 359-369, 2000
6. Pflug, J., et al., Honeycomb core materials: New concepts for continuous production, Sampe Journal, 39 (6), p. 22-30, 2003